

FUTURE SCENARIOS FOR CIRCULAR PLASTIC PACKAGING: STRATEGIC INSIGHTS FROM THE STOPP PROJECT

PROBLEM ENCOUNTERED AND OBJECTIVE

The packaging industry faces growing challenges due to environmental concerns and regulatory shifts. Plastic waste contributes significantly to pollution, making circular economy principles more urgent than ever. The STOPP project explores potential future scenarios for plastic packaging and identifies the key drivers shaping these transitions. The objective is to provide strategic insights for industry stakeholders, policymakers, and consumers to enhance circularity in packaging solutions. By understanding different possible futures, businesses and regulators can make informed decisions that support sustainability while maintaining economic viability.

MAIN RESULTS / OUTCOMES

The project presents four future scenarios: 'Pack it Easy!', 'Sustainably Yours!', 'Green by Law!', and 'Circular Synergies!'. Each highlights different regulatory and industry responses. Some focus on convenience and market forces, while others rely on regulation or collaboration. Without consumer demand or strong policies, progress may be slow. The study stresses the importance of aligning consumer behaviour with sustainable practices and providing financial incentives for adoption.

PRACTICAL RECOMMENDATIONS

Businesses should adopt sustainable designs, such as mono-material and biodegradable packaging. Policymakers must balance ambitious regulations with economic feasibility. Reuse operators should optimise collection systems for efficiency. Consumer campaigns should focus on clear labelling, digital tracking, and incentives. Collaboration across industries and policy sectors is essential for achieving a circular packaging economy.

Further information

The full report can be found on <https://stopp-project.eu/readiness-tools-resources/>

About this abstract

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STOPP is a Horizon Europe project aiming to transform food plastic packaging through the "5 Rs": Refuse, Reduce, Redesign, Reuse, and Recycle. Aligned with the EU's Packaging Directive, it develops training materials and strategies to promote circular economy solutions. Engaging stakeholders, STOPP advances recycling, reusable packaging, and consumer awareness for sustainable food packaging.

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